

The Impact of AfCFTA on Economic Growth: A Panel Data Analysis of African Countries

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Abstract

Intending to lift 50 million people out of extreme poverty, the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) started trading among its member countries in January 2021. The main objective of the AfCFTA includes reducing trade-related problems, smoothing investment opportunities, and removing trade barriers in African countries. This study uses panel data to examine the impact of foreign aid, inflation, the AfCFTA agreement, and external debt on the GDP of African countries. The annual data used in the analysis was collected from different data sources from 2000 to 2022. Out of 54 African countries, 35 were taken for study based on availability of data. A fixed effect panel regression model has been used in this study to establish the relationship between the GDP of African countries and the AfCFTA agreement, inflation, external debt, and foreign aid. The results indicate that the AfCFTA membership has a significant positive impact, highlighting the benefits of regional trade integration among African countries in fostering GDP.

Keywords: Africa, GDP, AfCFTA, FDI, Panel data

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1. Introduction

Most African countries have long challenges in reducing poverty and achieving sustainable economic growth. There are various reasons for this, like political instability, conflict with neighbor countries, dependence on other countries, insufficient infrastructure, environmental degradation, climate change and health challenges. To address these challenges, the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) was launched in January 2021, representing one of the largest free trade areas in the world (54 out of 55 African countries have signed this agreement). The main objective of AfCFTA is to reduce poverty, promote trade, increase investment, and improve infrastructure (Ijaiya et al., 2021). By facilitating trade and investment, the AfCFTA aims to lift 50 million people out of extreme poverty and enhance economic development across the continent. The agreement seeks to reduce trade-related problems, promote investment opportunities, and dismantle trade barriers among African nations.

Regional integration through free trade agreements like the AfCFTA is believed to be crucial for enhancing the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of African countries. However, several other factors, such as foreign aid, inflation, and external debt, also play a significant role in shaping the economic landscape of these nations. While the AfCFTA aims to provide a framework for economic growth through trade liberalization, it is essential to understand how this agreement, alongside other macroeconomic factors, influences the GDP of African countries.

This study addresses this knowledge gap by examining the impact of the AfCFTA, foreign aid, inflation, and external debt on the GDP of African nations using panel data from 2000 to 2022. The analysis includes 35 African countries selected based on data availability. A fixed-effect panel regression model is employed to explore the relationships among these variables, offering insights into how regional trade integration and other economic factors contribute to economic growth in Africa. The findings underscore the positive impact of AfCFTA membership on GDP, highlighting the importance of regional trade integration in fostering economic development.

The rest of the chapter is as follows: Section 2 discusses related literature, Section 3 discusses data and methodology used in this analysis, Section 4 discusses results, and Section 5 discusses conclusion and policy implication.

2. Related literature

The growth of any country depends on its holistic development, which encompasses improvement in both human and physical capital. However, many African countries depend on external support for their developmental needs. In this context, trade liberalization helps the development of a nation in many ways. By reducing trade barriers, countries can reduce their dependency and promote economic growth and diversification. There is an inverse relation between external debt and GDP (Ramamurti, 1992). Some studies have found the paradoxical relationship between external debt and GDP. When external debt reached 60 percent of GDP, annual growth declined by around 2 percent, whereas debt rose by more than 60 percent of GDP, and economic growth declined by 50 percent (Reinhart & Rudolf, 2010). Research by Levy (1988) finds that external economic aid and economic growth are positively correlated.

Most developing countries have a positive impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on their economic growth. FDI can deal with two major obstacles: shortage of financial resources and skill and technology (Owusu-Antwi et al., 2013). More of the emerging countries in Africa experience a shortage in capital supply; hence, there is a need for FDI. FDI can also be seen as cross-border financial investment between firms belonging to the same multinational group (Jannick et al., 2019) which fosters global economic integration and growth. Inflation is a crucial factor in determining the growth of the economy.

Inflation can impact GDP in both positive and negative ways (Batrancea, 2021). The level of inflation determines the growth level as a moderate level of inflation encourages spending and investment, so it contributes positively to the growth of GDP. In contrast, a high inflation rate is detrimental to the growth of GDP (Sequeira, 2021).

The empirical evidence provided shows that the economic effects of the AfCFTA rely largely on trade defense instruments such as eliminating import tariffs, reducing non-tariff measures (NTM), and improving trade facilitation as the source of enhancement to welfare of African countries (Störmer & Msweli, 2023).

3. Data and Methodology

The data used in this analysis is taken from the World Bank database for 35 African countries from 2000 to 2022 based on the availability. These countries are Algeria, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African

Republic, Comoros, Egypt, Arab Rep., Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mauritius, Morocco, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, South Africa, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. The description of variables taken into our analysis is added in Table 1. The sample characteristic of variables is reported in Table 2. The average external debt taken by selected African countries is around 12.5 billion during 2000-2022. The average inflation rate of selected African countries is around 7.4 per cent during the selected time period. On average, selected countries are receiving aid (grants) less than a billion.

Table 1: Description of variables

Variables	Description
GDP (billion)	The total value of Goods and Services produced in a country during a specific period
External Debt(billion)	The amount of money the country owes to foreign lenders (commercial banks, international financial institutions)
Aid (billion)	A grant in terms of money
Inflation rate(%)	Percentage change in cost of living or price of goods over a period
AfCFTA (dummy)	It takes value 1 for the year post-implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Area agreement.

Source: Author's estimation from the World Bank database

Table 2: Sample characteristics of variables

Variables	No of Observation	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
External Debt	759	12.59	25.39	0.13	190.73
Inflation rate	805	7.41	22.68	-9.61	557.20
Aid	805	0.77	0.96	-0.01	11.40
GDP	805	43.41	92.35	0.35	574.18

Source: Author's calculation

The correlation matrix of variables is reported in Table 3, and it indicates that variables are moderately correlated with each other. The test for multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity is conducted and added in Tables 4 and 5. The test for multicollinearity is done using variance inflation factor (VIF) test, and author find that its individual and average value of VIF is less than 10, indicating the absence of a multicollinearity problem in our dataset. The Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity indicates that the error term is not normally distributed, so we used robust panel regression in our analysis.

Table 3: Correlation matrix of variables

Variables	External Debt	Inflation rate	Aid	GDP
External Debt	1.00			
Inflation rate	0.02	1.00		
Aid	0.29	0.06	1.00	
GDP	0.77	0.02	0.38	1.00

Source: Author's calculation using STATA 17

Table 4: Multicollinearity test for variables

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
External debt	1.13	0.88
Aid (billion)	1.11	0.89
AfCFTA (Dummy)	1.03	0.96
Inflation rate	1.01	0.99
Mean VIF	1.07	

Source: Author's calculation using STATA 17

Table 5: Breusch-Pagan (Heteroskedasticity) test for variables

Ho: Constant Variance
Chi square = 426.37
Prob>Chi square = 0.00

Source: Author's calculation

4. Regression results

To analyze the impact of the African Continental Free Trade Area agreement on the economic growth of African countries, we estimate a fixed effect panel regression model. Using the Hausman test, we find that the fixed effect panel regression model is more appropriate than the random effect panel regression model. The result of the fixed effect panel regression model is reported in Table 6. The aid coefficient is positive and significant indicating that an increase in aid received by a country is associated with an increase in the GDP of countries. The external debt coefficient is positive and significant, denoting that debt taken by foreign countries and international organizations increases their GDP through the multiplier effect on their output production. The inflation rate does not have a statistically significant impact on GDP, indicating that, within this model, inflation might not be a critical factor for impacting the GDP of selected African countries. The African Continental Free Trade Area agreement variable is positive and

significant, indicating that GDP is positively related to this agreement. The overall R-square is 61 percent, denoting the model to explain the 61 per cent variation in GDP is explained by selected variables.

GDP of selected African countries	
Aid (grant)	10.63*** (0.91)
External debt	1.43*** (0.24)
AfCFTA	9.50** (3.73)
Inflation rate	-0.007 (0.01)
Number of Observation	759
Number of groups	33
F-statistics	41.95
R-square	Within 0.32 Between 0.74 Overall 0.61

Source: Author's calculation

5. Conclusion

The economic growth of any country depends on many factors; in this chapter, we analyze a few factors which impact the growth of a country. This analysis has revealed several key findings, such as aid received by the country being statistically significant and positively impacting the GDP of a nation, suggesting that external financial support plays a crucial role in boosting the economic output of selected African countries. External debt is associated with an increase in GDP, indicating that borrowing or debt taken by country when managed effectively, can contribute to the economic growth of selected African countries. The African Continental Free Trade Area agreement coefficient is significantly and positively affecting the GDP. It highlights the importance of regional trade agreements in promoting economic activity and integration among African countries. In contrast, the inflation rate coefficient is negative and statistically not significant, implying that the inflation rate does not directly impact the driver of GDP changes in selected African countries. The model explains a substantial portion of GDP

variation, with an overall R-squared of 0.61. Notably, the between R-squared (0.74) is higher than the within R-squared (0.32), suggesting that the model better explains differences in GDP across countries than changes within individual countries over time. The finding suggests the importance of strategic borrowing, financial support, and regional trade agreements in driving economic progress in African countries.

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